
Imperfect verbs and their uses in the poetry of Abu Firas al Hamdani (a morphological and syntactic analysis)

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Abstract:

This research examines the use of imperfect verbs in poems related to pride in the Diwan of Abu Firas al-Hamdani from a morphological and syntactic perspective. Morphology focuses on the structure of the verb and its conjugations, while syntax focuses on its inflection. The study aims to identify poems related to pride that use defective present tense verbs in the Diwan of Abu Firas al-Hamdani. This research is a qualitative study with a desk-based design. The data consists of defective present tense verbs, and the sources of the data are poems related to pride in the Diwan of Abu Firas al-Hamdani, while the data collection methodology is based on documentation. The researcher found that the total number of defective present tense verbs in the poems related to pride in the Diwan of Abu Firas al-Hamdani reached 521 verbs. The researcher hopes that this research will be a useful reference for deepening the understanding of defective present tense verbs in terms of morphology and syntax, especially in literary works such as poems related to pride. She also hopes that this research will contribute to enriching educational material that helps clarify the subject of defective present tense verbs so that students can gain a deeper understanding of it. She also hopes that this research will serve as a reference for future researchers to conduct further studies, especially in analyzing other linguistic aspects in the poetry of Abu Firas al-Hamdani or other Arabic literary works.

Keywords: Imperfect verbs, pride poems, grammar and morphology.

INTRODUCTION

The Arabic language plays an important role in human life, especially for Muslims. In general, it can be said that the role of the Arabic language is limited to three roles: its role in religion, science, and society. (Muradi, 2011) The role of the Arabic language in religion is as the language of the Holy Quran, the Prophetic Hadith, and classical Arabic books, which are considered sources of knowledge and guides for the lives of Muslims around the world. The importance of the Arabic language is influential in aspects of Islamic studies, as stated in the Holy Quran in Surah Yusuf, verse 103. (Ministry of Religious Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia, 2015)

Ibn Kathir interpreted this verse by saying, "Because Arabic is the most eloquent, clear, and comprehensive language, and the most suitable for conveying the meaning that is in the soul." Muhammad Quraish Shihab explains in his book *Tafsir al-Musbah* that "this verse clearly states and confirms that the Quran is in Arabic, and that Allah, the Exalted, chose that language. If this is the case, then the divine revelation that was conveyed to the Prophet ﷺ did not only convey the meaning, but also the structure of the sentence, word for word, all of which were chosen and compiled directly by God Almighty. The Arabic language was chosen to convey God's instructions in the Holy Quran due to its uniqueness compared to other languages. The Arabic language belongs to the Semitic language family, along with Hebrew, Aramaic, Chaldean, Syriac, and Babylonian. Arabic words generally consist of three consonants that can be formed in different ways. Arabic language expert Othman bin Jini (932-1002 AD) emphasized that the choice of Arabic vocabulary letters was not purely coincidental, but contained a unique linguistic philosophy. For example, the three letters that make up the word "said" (قال) are "q" (ق), "a" (أ), and "l" (ل), which can be formed into six different words, each with a different meaning. However, they all contain a basic meaning that unites them. Hence, the Arabic language has a remarkable ability to generate new meanings from existing word roots. In addition, Arabic is a rich language. This is not only evident in "gender" or in the numbers it denotes, such as singular, dual, and plural, or in the different tenses in which the present, past, and future are used, but also in its vocabulary and synonyms.

Linguists define a person as a good speaker if they can express the message they want to convey in words or sentences. For example, the phrase "the best speech is concise and meaningful" is useful for clarifying the message they want to convey. If the vocabulary of the language is limited, the intended meaning cannot be fully conveyed. (Shihab, 2002).

The above explanation provides an overview of the characteristics of the Arabic language compared to other languages, so it is not surprising that Arabic was chosen as the language of the final revelation, which is a refinement of the previous revelation that was sent down to the Prophet ﷺ, who was the best of the prophets and messengers and the seal of them, after whom there will be no other prophets. It can be concluded that God chose Arabic as the language of the Holy Quran because of its rich vocabulary and its ability to express the deep meaning of the roots of the words themselves. Therefore, the Arabic language allows the Holy Quran to convey divine guidance with precision and clarity, not only in the content of its meaning but also in the structure of its sentences and words. This is something that other languages do not have.

Among the many features of the Arabic language, there is also one that is very popular among Arabic language observers, namely its grammatical richness. Arabic grammar rules include two types of rules: syntax and morphology. Syntax rules determine the function of each word within a

sentence, regulate the endings of words, and determine how they are inflected (i.e., their endings change depending on their position in the sentence). Morphological rules, on the other hand, deal with the structure of Arabic words and the changes that occur in them due to addition or deletion.

In Arabic, words are divided into three categories: nouns, verbs, and particles. A noun is a word that has a meaning in itself and is not associated with time. A verb is a word that indicates an action or event that occurs at a specific time, whether in the past, present, or future. Verbs in Arabic are closely linked to time. A particle is a word that conveys meaning in relation to something else. Understanding nouns, verbs, and particles is important for analyzing the sentence structures found in Arabic texts.

In terms of conjugation rules, verbs are divided into three categories based on when they occur: past, present, and imperative. The past tense verb indicates an action that occurred in the past. (Muhammad al-Tunji and Ragi al-Asmar, n.d.) The present tense verb indicates an action or events that occur at the time of speaking (now) or after it (in the future). The imperative verb is used to request that something happen after the time of speaking. **Fouad Neama, Summary of Arabic Grammar, p. 77.** Thus, verbs are divided into three categories: past tense verbs, present tense verbs, and imperative verbs. Past tense verbs refer to actions or events that occurred in the past. The present tense refers to actions or events that are happening at the time of speaking or will happen in the future. Meanwhile, the imperative refers to a request that is to be fulfilled in the future. Understanding the types of verbs allows for the correct use of verbs according to the intended temporal context and makes it easier to identify verbs in Arabic texts.

Verbs are divided into two categories based on their structure: correct and defective. A correct verb is one whose letters do not contain vowels. An irregular verb, on the other hand, is one in which one or two of its original letters are vowels, namely alif, waw, and yaa at the beginning, middle, or end of the word, such as *ورث*, *باع*, and *رمى*. In terms of conjugation, defective verbs are somewhat more complex because the order of the letters does not seem to follow the pattern (fa'ala). If you want to compare them, you will find a big difference between the two in terms of their letter structure. To make it easier to understand the conjugation of defective verbs, one method is to understand the division of defective verbs, which are divided into four categories: example, hollow, deficient, and twisted (separated and joined). (عبدہ الراجعی, 1973) The example is when the first letter is a vowel, such as (*وجد*) and (*يسر*). The hollow is when the second letter is a vowel, such as (*قال*) and (*باع*). The deficient is when the *lām* is a vowel, such as (*dā'a*) and (*rama*). The coupled is when the vowels are joined, such as (*tawā*) and (*nāwi*), and the separated is when the vowels are separated, such as (*wāfā*) and (*wāqi*). (Mustafa al-Ghalayini, 1994) Therefore, the conjugation of defective verbs is not uniform, because the change in letters in words can vary depending on the

position of the vowel in the word. This is the main difficulty in analyzing the use of defective verbs. Therefore, it requires a deep understanding of the conjugation of defective verbs.

In terms of grammar rules, verbs are divided into two types: fixed verbs and inflected verbs. A fixed verb is one whose ending does not change depending on its position in the sentence. Past tense verbs and imperative verbs are always fixed verbs. An inflected verb is one whose ending changes depending on its position in the sentence. The present tense verb is originally inflected unless it is connected to the nun of women or the direct nun of emphasis. Therefore, the use of the present tense verb in a sentence may differ, and its inflection changes according to its position in the sentence and the factors that affect it (noun factors and verb factors).

Other than that, according to Ste Khadija et al. in their research entitled "Analysis of the Present Tense in the Quran, Surah Yasin." Ste Khadija et al. chose the present tense as the subject of their research because there are many students who make mistakes in pronunciation and understanding, such as not understanding the forms of pronouns in the present tense and not understanding the changes that occur in its movement when the factors of jussive or accusative are introduced. Based on these problems related to the present tense, especially its defective forms, the researcher conducted an in-depth study of defective present tense verbs in the poetry of Abu Firas al-Hamdani using morphology and syntax.

Abu Firas al-Hamdani's full name is al-Harith ibn Abi al-Ala Sa'id ibn Hamdan ibn Hamdun al-Hamdani, and his nickname is "Abu Firas." Abu Firas was born in 933 AD/321 AH in Manbij, a Syrian town north of Aleppo. He was orphaned at the age of three and raised by his mother and his cousin Saif al-Dawla. Abu Firas settled in the Hamdanid lands in Aleppo. Abu Firas studied literature and poetry. Abu Firas al-Hamdani is considered one of the most distinguished Arab poets, especially in his era, due to his distinctive poetic language and use of various linguistic styles, which earned him a high status among poets. (Nabaa Abdul Amir Abdul, 2020) For this reason, the researcher attempted to examine this linguistic and identify the uses of verbs in his poetry. Verbs in the Arabic language have several different forms, and poets tend to use different linguistic techniques to achieve their goals. Therefore, this research focuses on the imperfect verb to identify the types of imperfect verbs used by poets.

Abu Firas al-Hamdani succeeded in composing many poems. These poems were collected in a collection known as Diwan Abu Firas al-Hamdani. Most of the poems were characterized by pride, flirtation, lamentation, description, wisdom, and various emotions. Among the poems composed by Abu Firas al-Hamdani, those related to pride are characterized by the frequent use of imperfect verbs of various types, both in terms of morphology and syntax. Based on the results of the researcher's study of Abu Firas al-Hamdani's Diwan, the researcher found approximately 521 defective present tense verbs with different structures and in different Arabic positions in the poems

related to pride. Among the defective present tense verbs that can represent the contents of Abu Firas al-Hamdani's Diwan are the following:

First example, "Building the Example" in Poetry 99

When will the days come, like me, who is strong in adversity,
how many young men unyielding?

(تَلْدُ) is the defective present tense verb from the waw construction, because the letter waw is a defect in the fa of the verb. Its past tense is (وَلَدَ) on the pattern of (فَعَلَ). (تَلْدُ) originally comes from (تَوَلَّدَ) on the pattern of (تَفَعَّلَ). The waw, which is the fa of the verb, has been omitted because its past tense has three letters. Its fa is a waw in the pattern of fa'ala yaf'ul. As for the inflection of (taledu), it is a present tense verb raised because it is free of accusatives and conjunctions, and the sign of its raising is the apparent damma at the end because it is a correct present tense verb and nothing is connected to its end.

A second example of hollow construction in poetry (186) is the poet's statement:

And I was not afraid that you would refuse, even though there were two gulfs between us and the narrow path and the steep slope, as mentioned in the Diwan of Abu Firas al-Hamdani (p. 197). The word (أَبَيْتَ) is a defective present tense verb of the hollow ya'i construction, because the vowel (ya) is in the root of the verb. Its past tense is (بَاتَ), and its root is (بَيْتَ) on the pattern of (فَعَلَ). The root of (أَبَيْتَ) is (أَبَيْتُ) on the pattern of (أَفْعَلُ). The movement of the yaa was transferred to the baa because the root of the verb is yaa and it is preceded by a valid consonant, so the movement was heavy on the vowel and was transferred to what precedes it, and the word became (أَبَيْتَ). As for its inflection, it is a present tense verb marked with (أُنْ), and the sign of its accusative case is the apparent fathah at the end because it is correct at the end and nothing is connected to it.

A third example of the imperfect construction in poetry (99) is the poet's statement:

I wore the garment of my tormentor for days, but I did not wear the garment of patience. The word (أَنْضُو) is a defective present tense verb with a waw construction, because the vowel (waw) is in the lām of the verb. Its past tense is "nada" and its root is "nadawa" on the pattern of "fa'ala." The root of "anadu" is "anadu" on the pattern of "af'alu," but the waw was omitted because of the heaviness of the damma on it, so it became "anadu." As for its inflection, it is a present tense verb conjugated with (لم), and the sign of its conjugation is the deletion of the vowel because it is defective at the end.

A fourth example of the construction of the laff in poetry (32) is the poet's saying:

He relocates everyone who takes refuge with him and concludes with the relocation of homes. The word (بَأْوِي) indicates the defective present tense verb from the separate construction of the verb, because it contains two vowels: the hamza in its fa and the waw in its lam. Its past tense is

(أَوَى) on the pattern of (فَعَلَ). Its inflection is a present tense verb raised by the estimated damma on the yaa, prevented from appearing by the heavy sound.

(يَأْوِي) is a defective present tense verb of the coupled construction, because the vowels are vowels in the root of the verb and the lām of the verb. Its past tense is (أَوَى), whose root is (أَوَى) on the pattern of (فَعَلَ). (يَأْوِي) is originally (يَأْوِي) on the pattern of (يَفْعَلُ). The yaa movement was omitted because of the heaviness of the dhamma on it, so it became (يَأْوِي). (al-Khathib' Abdul Lathif Muhammad, 2003) As for the interpretation of (يَأْوِي), it is a present tense verb raised because it is free of accusatives and conjunctions, and the sign of its raising is the estimated damma on the yaa due to its heaviness, because it is a present tense verb with a defective ending and nothing is connected to its end.

Considering the issues raised, the main reason that prompted the researcher to choose this topic consists of several factors. First, the researcher's interest in the present tense, which differs from the past tense and the imperative tense in terms of their inflection. The past tense and the imperative tense are always inflected, while the present tense is originally uninflected unless it is connected to the nun of women or the direct nun of emphasis. Second, defective verbs differ from other verbs in terms of their inflection as well, because they are often inflected in a way that is estimated. These two factors are the main reasons that led the researcher to choose this topic. Third, the researcher focused on studying defective present tense verbs in poems related to pride in the Diwan of Abu Firas al-Hamdani using morphology and syntax, because the Diwan of Abu Firas al-Hamdani contains many examples of defective present tense verbs with different structures (e.g., ajaww, naqis, and lafiif) and in different Arabic positions (raised, lowered, and suspended). Therefore, the researcher will conduct research under the title "Imperfect Verbs and Their Uses in the Diwan of Abu Firas al-Hamdani (A Morphological and Syntactic Analysis)."

RESEARCH METHOD

Based on the type of research and its outputs, this research falls under qualitative research, as the researcher uses a qualitative approach to explain and describe the phenomena studied in a detailed and comprehensive manner. Based on the data source, this research is conducted as desk research. This type of research includes a set of activities related to data collection methods from desk sources, such as reading, note-taking, and processing various research materials from documents, scientific journals, books, historical stories, reports, or previous studies that can be referred to when preparing scientific research.

The approximation of the research contributes to ensuring that the steps followed by the researcher are consistent with the appropriate theoretical framework, as the researcher relies on the sciences of grammar and morphology to analyze defective present tense verbs and their uses in poems dealing with the theme of pride in the poetry collection of Abu Firas al-Hamdani.

The sources of data in this research are the imperfect verbs found in the poems of pride in the Diwan of Abu Firas al-Hamdani, and they are divided into two main sources: the primary source, which is the Diwan of Abu Firas al-Hamdani itself, and the secondary source, which is a collection of books, magazines, research reports, and previous studies that have addressed the subject of the research.

The researcher relies on a documentation approach to collect data, which involves several stages, beginning with a careful reading of Abu Firas al-Hamdani's poetry collection, followed by a search for poems related to pride that include defective present tense verbs, which are then carefully recorded and collected for analysis.

Data analysis involves several stages, including verifying the collected data on defective present tense verbs, reducing it by selecting and sorting the relevant data, then classifying these verbs according to their structure (such as example, hollow, defective, or twisted), analyzing them according to their grammatical positions (raised, lowered, or suspended), Finally, the results of the analysis of defective present tense verbs in the poems of pride in the Diwan of Abu Firas al-Hamdani are presented.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on her research into poems relating to pride, the researcher found 521 defective present tense verbs. In the poems containing defective present tense verbs, the researcher underlined the words containing the defective present tense verbs, as follows.

N O	Poem number	Poem	Defective Present Tense Verbs
1	1	O you who ponder their thoughts, to what extent # does the soul tire itself, will <u>it reach</u> the sky?	You will reach it.
2	1	My family, <u>I do</u> not <u>say</u> this out of pride, but they are noble # in my estimation, a source of pride and joy.	I say
3	13	And <u>I will</u> never <u>forget</u> the day of the cave # Veiled, her words were veiled	I forget
4			I forget
5	13 (2)	Her relatives called you a bad neighbor # for what <u>you</u> do not want and what you do not love	You want
6	13 (8)	And you continued, as you always have, <u>to do</u> good # <u>and protect</u> the harem, and <u>care for</u> the lineage	You take care
7			Protect
8			Care for

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9	13 (10)	So turn away from her, and <u>they will</u> redeem her # and lift up from her tail what has <u>been withdrawn</u>	They will redeem
10	13 (11)	<u>They call out</u> among the houses # T: ((May God not cut off the offspring of the Arabs!	They call out
11	14 (2)	I <u>did</u> not <u>count</u> my glories # And the praises of my noble fathers	I recount
12	22	Woe to you; who will fight the war if <u>we do</u> not? # And who <u>will sacrifice themselves</u> for it?	We will be
13			sacrifice
14			sacrifice
15	22 (3)	And who will surround the army from its flanks? # And who <u>will lead</u> the charge or strike the heart?	He leads
16	22 (6)	Do you threaten us with war as if we were # And you did not bind our hearts with it?	Promise
17	22 (13)	Did not our swords kill and capture them? And the lions of evil, even if they froze in terror?	Destroy
18	22 (15)	We left you in the belly of the wilderness, roaming it # as the jackal roams, licking the dust	Roam
19	24 (7)	Didn't you see us as the dearest of people, our neighbors, and the most powerful of them, our masters, our guardians?	You see
20	24 (9)	We prefer to sleep and not <u>be disturbed</u> , and <u>we are described</u> as beautiful, and <u>we are not answered</u> .	We are not envied.
21			Describe d
22			We are not rejected
23	24 (26)	As if (Nadi ibn Ja'far) led them # Gifts that he <u>did</u> not <u>desire</u> as a reward	He desires
24	24 (31)	And we drove them to (Al-Hayran) # as <u>we drive</u> difficult cattle	We drive
25	24 (32)	And we turned away (the furqulus) We did not want it # As if we were avoiding water	We wanted
26	24 (35)	And they cut (the sahsah) <u>and cut</u> a cheek # And they chose the wilderness with us, choosing	They dig
27	24	In front of a mourner, hearing with the soul # It is difficult for the tribe to <u>be afflicted</u>	Be afflicted

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28	24 (45)	And his doctrines were not narrow, but # <u>he feared</u> zeal, that <u>they might fear</u>	Fear
29			They are feared
30	24 (46)	And they command us, so we suffice him with the enemies # They are capable, if they wish, suffice and suffice	We will suffice
31			He wills
32	25	Are you surprised that we have conquered the earth by force, # and that our pillows <u>are necks</u> ?	Become
33	25 (5)	So be patient, for we have been given dominion # over a situation that is neither blameworthy nor <u>reprehensible</u> .	blamed
34	30 (1)	<u>I refuse</u> , as if I were a companion of youth # and of sleep, since the mixture has become clear, I refuse	I refuse
35	30 (3)	But I still hope and <u>fear</u> # The separation is imminent, and the heart is playful	I fear
36	30 (10)	My enemies multiplied over what befell me # As if <u>they did not wake up</u> except with my captivity	Repent
37	30 (11)	<u>They say</u> : "He did not consider the consequences of his actions." # And like me, those upon whom the consequences <u>fall</u>	They say
38			Befall
39	30 (13)	<u>I see</u> the fullness of my eyes, so I wade through it # Since death is before me and behind me are faults	I see
40			I wade
41	30 (14)	And indeed, behind determination there are and beneath it # situations <u>that are forgotten</u> without them, experiences	are forgotten
42	30 (15)	Men <u>who spread</u> rumors, and we have # things stored up for them and faults	They spread
43	30 (18)	He threw off the cloak of humiliation when he met him # as spiders <u>throw off</u> dust	They wear
44	30	And it is my honor that <u>he continues</u> to criticize. me # Envious of the matter that is blameworthy	continues
45			blaming me
46	30 (21)	For I <u>see</u> only an enemy who is at war # And another who is better than him in my eyes, the warrior	I see
47	37 (1)	And <u>do not describe</u> war to me, for it is # my food since childhood and my drink	Describe
48	42	And nothing <u>remains</u> of me but a broken heart # And promises on the teeth of time, a cross	Remain
49	42	I was satisfied with myself: (it was not successful) #	Satisfied

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		And my soul <u>was not satisfied</u> : (it was not successful)	
50	44	And <u>I desire</u> nothing but my gratitude as a reward # And indeed, gratitude is one of the best rewards	I want
51	52	<u>I am overcome</u> with grief! # From behind your veil and hijab!	I weep
52	54 (2)	The shield does not protect me from its owner # Nor <u>do I protect</u> the white and the black	I protect
53	54 (3)	<u>I will not return</u> with my mercy unbroken # Nor <u>will I</u> <u>go</u> with my sword unsheathed	I will return
54			I will go
55	54 (4)	Until your enemies <u>say</u> to you reluctantly: # (Your cousin has become the knight of the Arabs)	You will say
56	54 (6)	O you who are wary of <u>laying</u> a hand on me # Why do I see you allowing the white people of India to harm me?	Go ahead
57			I see
58	54 (8)	I still deny it, out of kindness; and I reject it # Nu'ma, and I am filled with wonder and amazement.	I am overwhel med
59	54 (9)	Until I saw you among the people, avoiding me # <u>You</u> <u>praise me</u> with a face that is not angry	You praise me
60	54 (10)	Then, with the eyes of the people upon me, I knew that you had not erred and <u>I had not been right</u> .	Hit
61	58	For war throws me with the whiteness of its men # And time strikes me with the blackness of its daughters	Throws
62	60 (2)	Tomorrow the horsemen will call me; and the qana # will return to the edge of the dune every renegade:	You call
63	68 (5)	And <u>I see</u> no corruption in corruption # That brings good to both sides	I see
64	82 (10)	My companions <u>say</u> , and the night is dark # And the morning breeze has blown upon us:	He says
65	82	The night has taken away our secrets, so can you <u>bring</u> us peace?	Relax
66	82 (13)	The desire to <u>be called</u> (Abu Firas), # Among friends, Mamun al-Jimah	It is said
67	82 (16)	And we are not stingy, <u>we protect</u> # the water and the permissible pasture	We protect
68	82 (17)	And we are not sinful, for <u>we protect</u> # the impregnable house and the abundant wealth.	Towards

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69	82 (20)	And what of wealth <u>that tells</u> of its owners # And becomes in the hands of the stingy	It tells
70	82 (23)	To the most generous of them, if he is generous, # And the most generous of them is the one who pushes away the stingy.	The most generous
71	82	You see him, when the victorious warriors tighten their reins # The fiercest of the Persians in battle	Tara
72	82 (27)	And <u>she weeps</u> in his presence # With her tears, and smiles at his	She cries
73	82 (29)	And <u>I am not satisfied</u> with justice from anyone but you # And I <u>overlook</u> your blatant injustice	I am satisfied
74			I overlook
75	82	If I do not <u>dissuade</u> the evil of suspicion # I extend my excuse in permissible abandonment	Deter
76	82 (45)	And I am not, even if I am patient with the trials # <u>I will leave</u> my family, and with them <u>I will leave</u>	I will not
77			I will not
78	82	To God, <u>I complain</u> of a group of my clan # <u>who mistreat</u> me with their words, in my absence and in my presence	I complain
79			They mistreat me
80	82 (8)	So do not promise me any favor, for when it comes # my family is more deserving of it, and if they become enemies	Count
81	88 (1)	To God, <u>I complain</u> about what <u>I see</u> from the tribes. # When we approach them, their ignorance increases	I complain
82			I see
83	88 (2)	And indeed, we are swayed by our emotions # towards them, even if their ways are truly bad	Bend
84	88 (3)	And the injustice of the tribe prevents us # from harming it, even if <u>we sought</u> to harm it, we would be guided	We seek
85	88 (6)	But I see it_God has improved its condition # and replaced it with wisdom_it has lost its wisdom	I see
86	88 (7)	How long shall we turn the white ones away from them, O Sadi? # <u>And bend</u> the breasts of the horses, which are filled with hatred	We bend
87	88	And we overcome their zeal with forbearance # And	We care

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		<u>we care for</u> men whom we do not <u>care for</u> ?	for
88			We care for
89			I fear
90	88 (9)	<u>I fear</u> for myself, and war is imminent # A calamity we cannot <u>bear</u>	We cannot bear
91			We throw
92	88 (11)	And we <u>will cast</u> ignorance with ignorance once # If we <u>find</u> no other way out	We find
93	90 (14)	And when worries multiply, nothing can relieve them # except patience, trust, and perseverance	Did not suffice
94	90 (18)	And I am the one whom the people knew # that only the generous master could nurture him	Grow
95			He gives
96	90 (21)	<u>He gives</u> when the clouds are stingy; out of generosity; # And <u>he protects</u> when times are hard	He protects
97			Exists
98	90 (22)	And glory <u>is found</u> among us in its essence, # And shame and obscenity <u>are not found</u>	Exists
99	90 (25)	If he had seen her (beloved), <u>he would not have said</u> # (She returned to him with ignorance and threat)	He would say
100	91	We have come to you; the least we can do is respond to you; our effort # is easier than the gait of the horses beneath us.	We respond
101			We approach
102			Generate s
103	91 (6)	<u>And we approach</u> with a closeness that does not <u>breed</u> boldness # <u>And we dry up</u> with a dryness that does not breed asceticism	We dry up
104			Generate s
105			It is repeated
106	91 (13)	<u>It is repeated</u> as you have accustomed, and its rock is solid # And with it <u>is built</u> lasting glory and praise	Built
107			Goes
108	96 (2)	And there is no good in abandoning one's tribe # He who <u>goes</u> against the tribe; or <u>becomes</u>	He becomes
109	99 (3)	And what is captivity from what I have endured in bearing it; # And what is the matter from what <u>I say</u> to him: I have	say

Imperfect verbs and their uses in the poetry of Abu Firas al Hamdani (a morphological and syntactic analysis)

110	99 (4)	And it has not escaped me that a person, exposed # to the arrows of enemies, if he is not struck, it is as if he has been	hit
111	99 (5)	And I do not <u>care</u> if I achieve a goal <u>that is</u> cheap, or a mark that is provided	I care
112			it
113	99 (6)	But I <u>choose</u> the death of my father's sons # on horseback, without a pillow	I choose
114	99 (7)	And I <u>refuse</u> and refuse to die, cushioned # by the hands of the Christians, a slow, painful death	I refuse
115			to die
116	99 (8)	I have worn the garment of my torment for days, but I <u>have not worn</u> the garment of patience.	I wear
117	99 (13)	For those like you <u>are called</u> to every greatness # And those like me <u>are redeemed</u> with every blackened	Called
118			Redeemed
119	99 (14)	I call you, not because I <u>fear</u> rejection # nor <u>do I hope</u> to delay until tomorrow	I call
120			I fear
121			I hope
122	99 (23)	And his destruction <u>was not</u> unexpected; except that they # blame him, since the ransom was paid, and he was not redeemed.	was
123			blamed
124	99 (28)	When <u>will</u> the days <u>give birth</u> , like me, to a boy for you who is strong in adversity and not distracted?	Give birth
125	99 (29)	If you <u>redeem</u> me, you <u>redeem</u> the honor of the Most High, # And hasten to return to Him, accustomed	You will redeem
126			You will redeem
127	99 (30)	And if you <u>redeem</u> me, you <u>redeem</u> your honor, # a boy who is not rejected by tongue or hand.	Redeem
128			You will be redeemed
129	99 (33)	Not everyone who desires wealth will attain it, nor will everyone who strives for glory <u>be guided to it</u> .	Attain
130			Guided
131	99 (35)	And if my soul <u>had not attained</u> your loyalty, I <u>would</u> not have mentioned it, in his victory, every source	Attain
132			I would be
133			I would have
134	99 (36)	Nor would I <u>have cast</u> the thousand, blue-eyed, # with seventy, among them all the most bitter	I would throw
135	99 (39)	And you are the Lord, whom I follow, # And you are	I follow

Imperfect verbs and their uses in the poetry of Abu Firas al Hamdani (a morphological and syntactic analysis)

136		the star, by which <u>I am guided</u>	I am guided
137	99 (43)	Did <u>you</u> not <u>see</u> that in you I shook hands with death, # and in you I drank death, without hesitation?	Did you see
138	99 (44)	<u>They say</u> : "Avoid it!" A custom I did not know? # It is difficult for a person who <u>is not accustomed to it</u> .	They say
139			Get used to it
140	99	But I will throw it away, for it is either a mere assumption or a solid structure of glory.	He threw
141	99 (47)	And <u>I did not know</u> that time is counted in the number of enemies; # And that the black maniacs <u>throw from the hand</u>	I know
142			Throw
143	99 (48)	You (son of Abdullah) remain <u>protected from destruction</u> , # <u>and a master after master will redeem you from us</u>	Protected
144			Redeemed
145	99	You remain (son of Abdullah) What has not yet dawned # <u>You go to the clear glory</u> , and <u>you transgress</u>	You go
146			Transgress
147	100	And <u>I have not seen</u> anyone like me today who is more envious; # As if the hearts of people, to me, are one heart	I see
148	100 (3)	<u>Has this era not seen</u> anyone other than me who is virtuous? And have the envious not prevailed over me with their envy?	He sees
149	100 (4)	<u>I see</u> hatred beneath hypocrisy, and I reap # from honey that is sweet, then bitter	I see
150	100 (6)	A little apology, whoever <u>spends the night with his sins</u> # Seeking the sublime, and earning praise	I stay
151	100 (16)	And O witness of the eyes in what disturbs me, # Indeed, my gaze is in harm, not witnessing	Doubt
152	100	If I wish, I will declare war on the enemy, and <u>I will not hesitate</u> # I turn my thoughts to the faces of the conspirators	I will not
153	100 (23)	And we <u>saw</u> that he who had changed his position did not succeed in such adversities.	We see
154			Pour
155	100 (24)	My foolishness Whoever <u>buys my</u> salvation with himself # And sins are removed from me, without praise	Buy
156	100 (28)	For you have brought about the death of Hudhayfa, # and he saw it as a preparation for hardship.	He sees

157	100	May God <u>bring</u> good; for I have # returns from His blessings, not losses.	Come
158	100 (32)	How many times has He lifted me from the depths of darkness? <u>Was there</u> no <u>one</u> to rescue me from its depths, no crowd of supporters?	Be
159	100	God saved (Al-Muhallab) openly, and (Al-Hajjaj) <u>was</u> not asleep about him.	Be
160	100	And he died imprisoned (Zaban ibn Munzir) # <u>Sold</u> at the highest price (in Mecca) like unsold goods	Sold
161	100 (42)	I will be patient, either finding what I want, # thanks to (Ibn Abdullah) or not finding it	I want
162	100	And if <u>it is</u> the latter, then I am not immortal # nor is the arrogant mocker immortal either.	Be
163	100 (46)	Creatures that do not <u>exist</u> in all that is glorious # But they are in the glorious son of the glorious	They exist
164	125 (4)	<u>We choose</u> from them the beautiful # and the brave	We choose
165	125 (9)	Whoever was like me did not <u>stay</u> # except as a prisoner or a prince	Stay
166	126 (1)	If you wish to <u>encounter</u> fierce lions, # let us be the ones who will never be defeated.	You will encounter
167	126 (2)	You will be met by all of us, O Samid, # who will fight until the army is defeated.	He will meet
168	126 (4)	We intended to strike the enemies in the midst of their homes # with a blow that would be seen, from its impact, the sky would be darkened	It is seen
169	126 (6)	And ask (Numayr) on the day he went to them, # <u>Did they</u> not <u>believe</u> in death when they were scattered?	They were certain
170	126 (7)	And ask (Uqail) when she fled (to Tadmur) # Did we not strike her with a blow that would lead to her death?	We beat
171	126 (8)	And ask (Qushayr), when her throat was dry, # Did we not give her a cup to drink, from death, red?	Nasq
172	126 (11)	So he satisfied all their heroes, every bird and wolf, tomorrow <u>he will fold</u> the simple, A'fara	Folds
173	131 (2)	Will my sorrow be extinguished, and my eyes be satisfied, # and <u>I will</u> not <u>kindle</u> a fire with the invaders?	Light

Imperfect verbs and their uses in the poetry of Abu Firas al Hamdani (a morphological and syntactic analysis)

174	131 (3)	I saw patience as far <u>from hope</u> as possible, # when the army marched with the invaders.	Hopeful
175	131 (4)	And I prepared the battalions, marked, # Calling out, every moment, to me: Suara!	They call
176	131 (7)	With horses that do not resist those who ride them, # And people who do not <u>see</u> death as shameful	They see
177	131 (8)	behind the caravans in every land, # and the first to change, when they change.	He changes
178	131 (12)	<u>So I heal</u> my chest from the wounds of horses, # And I realize from the vicissitudes of time that I have risen	I heal
179	131 (21)	May God grant me his appearance, quickly, # and accompany him with safety, wherever he goes	I see
180	139 (29)	And a heart that accepts war, and he is a warrior # And determination <u>that sustains</u> the body, and he is a traveler	Uqim
181	139 (31)	If <u>I</u> do not <u>find</u> a tribe in every valley # Then the noble are tribes to the noble	Find
182	139 (33)	From the one <u>who refuses</u> to disobey her Lord # When she is stripped, at the cave, the aprons	Refuse
183	139 (34)	And fragile, thin, slow, her fatigue, # She takes on what the camels cannot <u>bear</u>	Can bear
184	139	How far apart are the two, and how close! # And how close is what the traveler <u>hopes for</u> !	He hopes
185	139 (43)	I settled in Qarmay (Ma'ad), both of them, # a place; I saw how the glories <u>were built</u> !	I see
186			are built
187	139 (46)	By your life, sight is of no use to its people, # if those who see <u>do not have</u> insight!	Be
188	139 (48)	I strive for the sake of my people, by His grace, # and I am proud, until <u>I see</u> no one to boast about.	I see
189	139 (49)	<u>And I strive</u> for a cause, which I consider to be attainable, # I agree with his opinions, and I support him	I strive
190	139 (50)	O rider, <u>driven</u> by the sticks of his journey # swift, agile, and swift!	Driven
191	139 (59)	(Abu Ahmad, wait! If the branch <u>is</u> not good, # then the elements will not be good on the Day of Pride!	Be good
192	139 (60)	<u>Do you call yourself</u> by what the first ones (Wail) called themselves; # when those first ones have been overwhelmed by the last ones?	Be exalted

Imperfect verbs and their uses in the poetry of Abu Firas al Hamdani (a morphological and syntactic analysis)

193	139 (62)	Upon me, for the first words and their meaning, # the glories that destroy him, and the glories <u>that remain!</u>	Tufni
194			Remain
195	139	I (Al-Harith) am the chosen one from the descendants of (Harith) # If <u>he does</u> not rule, among the people, except the best!	Fill
196	139	And among us is the one who added to the imam and his army! # And there is no existence except what the soldiers <u>add</u>	Add
197	139	How <u>can glory be attained</u> when the body is weak? How <u>can the desired be attained</u> when abundance is abundant?	It is attained
198			Attained
199	139 (74)	And despite the enemy, he will restore it # accustomed to closing the gap, and the gap is circular	He will restore
200	139 (80)	They obey what has become justice among them; # And there is no obedience to a person who is unjust	Obey
201	139 (85)	And he accepted (the buyer), <u>he is led</u> before him, # and for the shackles on both his hands, braids	He is led
202	139 (95)	So <u>he did not leave</u> any of them unstung by his stings # And <u>he did not leave</u> any of them unstruck by his repeated blows	He leaves
203			He remains
204	139	And he (Ibn Mazroo) responded <u>with his chest</u> , # And in his chest was what the probes <u>could not reach</u>	He groaned
205			Attain
206	139 (114)	So <u>you saw</u> nothing but a split in the sky, # and a sea beneath the clouds, churning!	You saw
207	139 (117)	If my elders <u>pass away</u> , their glory <u>will not pass away</u> , # nor will those lofty heights and deeds be forgotten.	Pass
208			Go
209	139 (118)	<u>We sing</u> as they sang, and <u>we build</u> as they built, # We have a past honor, and another present	We sing
210			We build
211	139 (120)	They, and the Prince of Believers, are displaced, # They sheltered him when <u>he found no one to take him in</u>	He finds
212			Neighbors
213	139 (124)	When the Arabs <u>forget</u> Amara # And among us there is one who seeks revenge, remembering	Forget
214	139 (127)	Then her captors <u>sing</u> her praises # And those are women who have no flowers	Sing
215	139 (133)	So do not impose on me a plan that I cannot bear # For your glory is overwhelming, and your favor is skillful	I can bear
216	139 (134)	And if my pride and your pride <u>were</u> not one # No one would praise me	Be

217	139 (143)	And he began <u>to change</u> his opinion from every angle, # and the decisive one forbade him, and the determined one commanded him.	He turns
218	139 (145)	And he drove (Numayr) the fiercest of the market in Qana, # so that no Shami <u>touched him</u> and no Jazir <u>sacrificed him</u> .	touch
219			sacrifice
220	139	When (Al-Ikhshid) saw what had befallen him, <u>he turned away</u> and hid his face.	Bent
221	139 (150)	He saw the son-in-law and the messenger, who is the one who makes the agreements, # through whom <u>he can achieve</u> what the armies cannot <u>achieve</u> .	Attain
222			Tanal
223	139 (152)	And he brought it to the belly (of the luqan) and its back # <u>They trample</u> with it the dead, light and swift	They tread
224	139 (155)	Those strongholds fall down before us, prostrating themselves, # And those fortresses <u>throw themselves</u> at us with their inhabitants	Throw
225	139 (158)	We struck with it the width of the Euphrates, as if # <u>it were walking</u> with us under the saddles of Algeria,	Walking
226	139 (159)	Until we reached (Arqanin) We drove it # And its heels and flanks were worn out	We drive
227	139 (160)	And it leaned to the right (with a tremor) # Majahid <u>recites</u> the patient and steadfast	Follow
228	139 (165)	He redeemed himself with a son who was like himself; # And for the deafening severity, the ammunition <u>is stored</u> !	Acquired
229	139	And I will rely on it on the Day of Battle! # Like it, in glory, the swords <u>are drawn</u> !	Bow down
230	139 (169)	If the sheikh does not bend, (and we stand) firm, # And in the chain are a thousand like lions, fierce	Twists
231	139 (170)	And only his son-in-law <u>remained</u> , and his daughter's son # And he stirred up the rest of those who were rebellious	Remains
232	139	And the easy speech may come early, and <u>I will reap</u> # The elders of a people that the young have not reaped	reap
233	139 (180)	They call him, and the rain <u>is hoped for</u> as if it were # on the balconies of the Romans, palm trees:	They call him
234			Hoped
235	139 (182)	We ask you for kindness, and we fear your wrath, # for you are mighty, and you are powerful!	We hope
236			Nakhshā
237	139 (184)	He will drive away (Ka'b) where there is no water to be	is hoped

		found, # so that you may know (Ka'b) which of your companions will remain steadfast.	for
238	139 (185)	And he seeks (Ka'b) where there is no trace <u>to follow</u> # so that (Ka'b) may know which stick to break	Followed
239	139 (188)	With us and with you, O sword of the state (of Hashim), # The sons of our uncles <u>grow tall</u> and boast!	They grow tall
240	139 (190)	<u>You see</u> which of us you have met from the sons of my father # He has a milker who does not <u>wake up</u> and a shearer	You see
241			Wakes up
242	139 (192)	And my brother, if <u>he</u> strives with his glory # Then neither death is feared, nor poison is harmful	Strives
243	139 (214)	If <u>I call out</u> in distress, he is a warrior; # And if <u>I strive</u> for greatness, he is a supporter.	I call
244			I strive
245	139 (215)	And when fear overshadowed (Rabia) # And nothing <u>remained</u> except what the graves protected	Remain
246	139 (220)	And indeed, they are the masters, and the treasures that # <u>I use</u> to outdo my opponents and multiply my wealth!	I prolong
247	139 (58)	And, despite the enemy, he will repeat it # accustomed to returning the gap, and the gap is circular	He will restore
248	139 (64)	And Baharoon came, <u>led</u> before him, # and for the shackles, in both his hands, braids	Led
249	139 (69)	He was led away as a bride <u>is led away</u> , bound with chains and strong shackles.	Unveiled
250	139 (70)	<u>He says</u> to him, and the interpreter explains: # (Can anyone who desires him be blamed?)	He says
251			He explains
252	139 (75)	Full of them, if <u>he found</u> no one but himself # Tears occupy the eyes, and throats	He finds
253	139 (92)	So he did not hide in fear, nor <u>did he escape</u> , # nor did he take refuge in a fortress, nor <u>did he give up</u> in confusion	Escape
254			Guided
255	139 (96)	And he (the son of Mazroo) returned, his chest <u>heaving</u> , # and in his chest was something that <u>could not be reached</u> by the probes.	He surges
256			Reach
257	139 (97)	And when (the buyer) became arrogant, our swords struck him # with the force of a dying man, whom the circles <u>did not</u> fear.	Fear
258	139 (99)	And a people who agreed to fight, so they became few in number. What <u>can</u> the critic <u>say</u> ?	He says

Imperfect verbs and their uses in the poetry of Abu Firas al Hamdani (a morphological and syntactic analysis)

259	139 (104)	They helped him when <u>there was</u> no one <u>left</u> to help him, # They supported him when there were few supporters left	Remain
260	139 (110)	So his stabbing <u>did not remain</u> hidden among them, #	Remains
261		And his repeated blows <u>did not remain</u> unnoticed.	Remains
262	139	And its domes were extended with the wings of (the Euphrates) # And none of the people of (the island) <u>remained</u>	Remain
263	139 (114)	And he responded to the footsteps (of Fadl ibn Ja'far) # He manages him from his enemies, and he confronts	He manages
264	139	And a small matter may become great, and the elders of a people <u>may reap</u> what the young have sown.	reap
265	139 (128)	And if forgiveness had not softened his heart, he would have been destroyed, and none of them <u>would have remained</u> (in the dust).	Remain
266	139 (130)	The women call out to him: (O Lord of Amir, # Will Amir perish after his deeds?)	They call out
267	139 (132)	We ask you for kindness, and we fear your wrath, # for	We hope
268		you are mighty, and you are powerful.	We fear
269	139 (137)	And he returned with it, <u>guiding it</u> to (Marj Qilz) #	Guides
270		Howadi guides it with guidance and insight	Guides
271	139	And he continues <u>to throw</u> every land with a legion # Seeing clearly the striking of horses with horses, skilled	He throws
272	139 (148)	He sacrificed himself for a son who was like himself; # And for the deafening intensity, the shields <u>protect</u>	Protect
273	139 (150)	And the king of Rome is wary of the place where he dwells; # And does the cautious one repel the available opportunity?	Yasim
274	139 (153)	But <u>you saw</u> nothing but a split in the sky # And a sea beneath the clouds, overflowing	You saw
275	139	The last of those I counted at the time of birth # And the first of those whom the claws <u>praise</u>	Praise
276	139	And she followed (fairly) the path of his swords; # Indeed, whoever <u>is judged</u> by the sword is unjust	passes judgment
277	139 (164)	I am Al-Harith) chosen from the family of (Harith) # If only the righteous men <u>are left</u>	Fill
278	147	I will thirst until the eggs and chicks <u>are fed</u> # And I will hunger until the wolf and the eagle are satiated	Be satisfied
279	147 (31)	And I will .not become the living dead in a cave # Nor	Come

		the army, unless the omen comes to me first	
280	147 (32)	And O Lord of the House, You did not hide me, impregnable # I rose upon it with the dawn, I and the dawn	Hide
281	147	And the one who pulls the reins toward me, I met her # But the harshness of the encounter did <u>not</u> meet her, nor did the roughness	meet
282	147 (36)	Nor did <u>he</u> overwhelm me with his rich garments; # Nor did he dissuade me from generosity	Overwhelm
283			Deter
284	147 (37)	And what need <u>have</u> I of wealth? <u>I seek</u> its abundance? # If <u>I</u> do not <u>flee</u> my honor, then there is no abundance	I seek
285			I flee
286	147 (39)	But if judgment is passed on a man # He has no righteousness to protect him, nor the sea!	Protect
287	147 (41)	But I will proceed, for there is no shame in it, and you have two choices, the better of which is captivity.	I proceed
288			Fault
289	147	<u>They say</u> to me: "You sold safety for destruction." # So I said: "By God, I have not suffered any loss."	They say
290	147 (43)	And will death <u>be spared</u> me for an hour, # if captivity and harm are spared me?	It will not be spared
291	147 (44)	It is death; so choose what is best for you to remember # For man <u>does</u> not <u>die</u> as long as he remembers	Die
292	147 (51)	And if others blocked it, I would not block it, they would be satisfied with it; # And the gold would <u>not have risen in price</u> if the yellow metal had been spent.	Rise
293	147	Our souls <u>are humbled</u> in the high places; # And whoever proposed to the beautiful woman, the dowry did not increase her value.	It is easy
294			Yaghl
295	151 (3)	I do not disobey him in committing sins; # In his desire, the fire <u>is sweet</u>	I disobey
296			Pleasant
297	151 (5)	<u>I remained</u> steadfast in my abandonment until # my patience waned and my supporters dwindled	Remain
298	162 (6)	He expels all those who <u>take refuge</u> with him # and seals it with the expulsion of the homes	Take refuge
299	162 (8)	And I said: (Gray hair is the least of what <u>I encounter</u> # in this world, and the easiest of what <u>I manage</u> !)	I encounter
300			I manage
301	162 (9)	(And my companion, the dawn, <u>does not remain</u> until # it embraces the dawning of the day)	Remains

Imperfect verbs and their uses in the poetry of Abu Firas al Hamdani (a morphological and syntactic analysis)

302	162 (12)	When <u>will I ask</u> without hesitation or fear # <u>that he will agree</u> with me, and without fear of rejection?	I ask
303			agree
304	162	<u>I see</u> myself demanding something of myself # A little, without its purpose, my limitation	I see
305	174 (16)	For I <u>rise</u> with the right of the sky # Then I <u>return</u> to the element	I rise
306			I return
307	186 (1)	And I was not <u>afraid</u> that <u>you would refuse</u> , for between us are two gulfs, the fragrant path and the sweet path.	I fear
308			You refuse
309	187 (2)	<u>I walk away</u> from her, and my heart remains with her # As if my horse were trapped by the weight of the journey	I walk
310	187 (5)	Like a pebble that is <u>thrown</u> forever # into the sky, <u>it rises</u> and then falls back	Thrown
311			Rises
312	190 (2)	And what I hope for from reaching him # When he shook the reins of my horse	I hope
313	190 (3)	I did not throw myself at the spears, nor <u>did I throw</u> the spear with a heart that was not stolen.	I would not
314	193 (1)	<u>I will never forget</u> what they said when they met me: # (The sword has struck the face of this wretched man!)	I forget
315	201 (1)	What is for the slaves from what # God <u>decrees</u> is abstinence	Decides
316	214 (3)	So who will protect the afflicted, whose heart is heavy with sorrow? The eyelids of his eyes have fallen upon him like swords!	Protect
317	214 (6)	The generous one is not the one who <u>is satisfied with</u> his life, # and <u>submits</u> to the vicissitudes of time if he is dry.	He is satisfied
318			Resigns himself
319	218 (1)	Others change him with harsh actions # And <u>turn him</u> away from the qualities of the truly generous	Prevents
320	218 (2)	I do not <u>accept</u> friendship if it does not <u>last</u> # In the face of indifference and lack of fairness	I accept
321			if it lasts
322	218 (3)	Woe to the greedy, for what they <u>bring</u> is little # in return fo.r their insistence and persistence	Comes
323	218 (6)	And I <u>am cured</u> of the greedy man's greed, my fatherhood, my chivalry, my modesty, and my chastity.	Recover
324	218 (10)	I do not <u>possess</u> the vicissitudes of my life # as if they	Acquire

Imperfect verbs and their uses in the poetry of Abu Firas al Hamdani (a morphological and syntactic analysis)

		were my allies	me
325	228	<u>I live</u> in debt with my mother's son; # And I bear witness for my friend against my brother	I abide
326	238 (3)	Those houses, and the people # Ib, I do not see them as good!	I see
327	238 (7)	<u>Tara Dar</u> (Wadi Ain Qa # Sir) A spacious, spacious house	Tara
328	238 (9)	Its brides <u>reveal themselves</u> to us # The buzzing of flies when they appear	Tajlo
329	242	And the spirit said to the bodies: This # will separate us if <u>you do not turn away!</u>	Turn
330	245 (39)	<u>He will be granted</u> forgiveness for every sinner # He has with us what you cannot <u>attain</u>	He will obtain
331			You will obtain
332	245 (43)	If I pray one day and <u>find</u> no one to pray with me, # and if I speak one day and <u>find</u> no one <u>to speak with me!</u>	I find
333			I find
334			Respond
335	925 (3)	He says, and my spear has been adjusted in it: # (For some reason, the men fought each other!)	He says
336	262	The days defend me from what I want, # just as the stubborn debtor paid off his debt.	I want
337	262 (10)	My friends, my goals are far from reach! # Can you help me with what <u>I am trying to do?</u>	I am trying
338	266 (2)	And <u>I care</u> for my relatives, # And I do not neglect the favor of my brother.	I care
339	266 (7)	And the neighborhood has been exhausted, from behind him, # And I stop, fearing the response, the first of it	I stop
340	266 (9)	And that is because I am fierce # I eat my flesh and do not entrust it to others!	I entrust
341	271 (4)	And <u>I</u> will not be judged After me # Little praise, condemned for his deeds	I will not
342	271 (5)	But I will destroy him, and <u>I will take</u> # treasures from his reward or beauty	I will destroy
343			I will acquire
344	271 (7)	And what <u>do</u> the warriors of our father's sons <u>reap</u> # except the fruits of the edges of the highlands	Gather

Imperfect verbs and their uses in the poetry of Abu Firas al Hamdani (a morphological and syntactic analysis)

345	271 (9)	If no fire <u>touches</u> me, then I # refuse to accept the fire of others, other than that which is right	Touch
346			I refuse
347	271 (14)	<u>We despise</u> his dwelling, and we are weary of it, # and our fathers prevent us from leaving	We are weary
348	271 (15)	Fearing that it will be said, throughout the land: # (The sons of Hamdan) have stopped fighting!	It will be said
349	271 (17)	And whoever returns to the battlefield will not be afraid # The trials of time in family and wealth	Fear
350	271	If my brothers respond in kind, then I will honor their position and respect their status.	would be
351	271 (02)	If no hand or heart betrays you, then you have no reason to fear the treachery of the nights.	Betray
352	271 (26)	You struck and <u>did</u> not <u>leave</u> the sword a limit # And you feared so much that you narrowed your field	Leave
353	271 (32)	She <u>said</u> : You have been rewarded well # for protecting the sanctity of the noble!	She says
354	272	<u>Shall I turn a blind eye</u> to something I do not want, # when my spear and sword <u>are ready</u> to defend me?	I will overlook
355			I want
356			To stand
357	272 (5)	He tempts them with good and evil, Majid, # a trap for the followers of the tailed Thursday	He rules
358	272 (13)	I walked with her, from the sorcerer of the sea, <u>I rose</u> # on (Kafr Tabin), her direction did not <u>change</u>	I set out
359			be changed
360	272 (14)	And I made my vow that <u>they would say</u> : You have betrayed us! # And I accepted, I did not tire, and I did not deceive	They say
361	272 (15)	To the Arabs, <u>do not fear</u> the victory of the victorious, # the pride of my tribe (Amir) and (Al-Muhajjal)	Fear
362	272 (19)	My uncle's daughters to not see me: # Far from being fair, or showing little favor	.They see
363	272 (25)	And if I <u>had</u> not been captivated by the turmoil of war between them # I would have followed the path of forgiveness from the outset	Miss
364	280 (4)	<u>He sees</u> (the flea), since he saved him from us, # he delayed his wife, and loved money	He sees
365	280 (5)	A slave girl from (Quraiz) <u>revolves</u> around him; # And the women ask him about the men!	They revolve

Imperfect verbs and their uses in the poetry of Abu Firas al Hamdani (a morphological and syntactic analysis)

366	280 (6)	<u>They say</u> to him: Safety is the best booty! # And indeed, the humiliation in that statement	They say
367	284 (1)	<u>He waves</u> his hand The boy from my father's sons; # And you recognize him from others by his features	He waves
368	285 (2)	And what <u>is</u> the glory of free will, one day, # if it is not reaped by the harvesters	You will enjoy
369			Gather
370	285 (3)	And we encounter, without it, the disheveled man # With the bitterness of stabbing, in the bitterness of the field	We encounter
371	286 (2)	I left with him women (the daughters of Kalab), # Fawarka, who <u>desire</u> men	They desire
372	286 (4)	A woman I loved, but # <u>I stay</u> in the monastery in Wasal	He stays
373	290 (4)	<u>And I am generous</u> , days I have settled, with dignity, # as if I were from my family I was transferred to my family	I am more spacious
374	291 (4)	This and this is our habit, # Blood <u>is shed</u> , and blood <u>is spilled</u>	Shed
375			Shed
376	291 (5)	Say to (the son of Warqa Ja'far), # until <u>he says</u> what he knows:	He says
377	291 (6)	(I, even if the mazaar # is far away, and I <u>am</u> not aware of it)	Be
378	291 (7)	<u>(I turn</u> to that khila # li, and <u>I choose</u> that shim)	I choose
379			I choose
380	293 (1)	Are they two sons, or two brothers? For I <u>see</u> the blood of the two shields as their sustenance.	I see
381	293 (2)	The insight <u>reveals</u> : that in their garments # there are two lions, whose protection the lions avoid	It foretells
382	293 (3)	Why <u>do they</u> not <u>surpass</u> the people in generosity? # And both of them, their grandfathers	surpass
383	293 (4)	<u>You receive</u> (the father of the storm) in their storm, # And you see the virtue of (the father of the sky) above them	Receive
384	293 (9)	But for those two, we have a lavish place, # which no one else among the people claims except them.	Claims
385	297 (2)	I did not <u>let</u> the girls of my people <u>speak</u> , # when they spoke, they stammered.	Let them speak.
386	297 (4)	And when <u>I found</u> nothing but escape # Stronger than	Find

Imperfect verbs and their uses in the poetry of Abu Firas al Hamdani (a morphological and syntactic analysis)

		death or a dove	
387	297 (14)	And I have become attached to him, # And I am content to <u>be</u> his servant	I am
388	300 (3)	And she asked me about myself, so I said, in amazement: # As if <u>you do</u> not <u>know</u> what an orphan is?	Do you know
389	300 (4)	Lend me your ear, I will spare you the evil, a glance of pity # Perhaps <u>you will</u> mourn, or perhaps you will have mercy!	I will protect you
390			You will pity me
391	300 (6)	<u>And I am satisfied</u> with what <u>you are satisfied</u> with, with discontent and satisfaction # And I <u>turn</u> a blind eye, knowing that you are wronging me	I am satisfied
392			You are satisfied
393			I overlook
394	300 (11)	I am eager to see you, but it is forbidden, and the fire of sorrow burns between us.	I see
395	300 (12)	And I stop <u>crying</u> over you, flying away, # And my heart cries, and my wings beat	I cry
396			Weeps
397	300	I will cry for you, for I have no time left # If tears are precious to me, then blood is not precious to me	I cry
398	300 (17)	And my judgment is the crying of time in what replaces me, # And the judgment (of Labid) in it is a criminal act.	It replaces me
399	300 (24)	When the nights <u>did</u> not <u>strike</u> us, the son of determination # The turning of fate weighs heavily on him, so he bears it	Hit
400	300 (25)	War <u>humiliates</u> us, our dear soul # When praise and flattery are withheld from us	Humiliate
401	300 (27)	And we are people whose hearts <u>still</u> have a place to drink, among the manaya, and a place to eat.	still
402	300 (29)	<u>And we call</u> generous those who <u>give</u> of their wealth, # and those who give of themselves are most generous	We call
403			Generous
404	300 (30)	And why should I not proceed, Hamid! My goal is far away, and my actions are not blameworthy.	I proceed
405	300 (31)	If fleeing <u>does</u> not <u>save me</u> from destruction, # then patience is more desirable and more decisive.	Be
406			save

Imperfect verbs and their uses in the poetry of Abu Firas al Hamdani (a morphological and syntactic analysis)

407	300 (35)	And <u>we will defeat them</u> , behind the bay with a damper # Some of its waves are blood	Wading
408	300 (39)	I saw them <u>seeking</u> revenge for the past, # and every day the sword takes from them	They seek
409	300 (42)	And the white ones did not <u>betray</u> you in every scene # But killing the sheikh among us is forbidden	Repent
410	301 (3)	And our command is carried out in every neighborhood, # so that speech brings him closer <u>and</u> excludes him.	It will bring him closer
411			Exclude
412	301 (6)	And they turned to meet each other, some with others, # for them _ and the earth is spacious _ crowding	Meet
413	301 (7)	They were happy, and the night brought us together, but # <u>reveals</u> them, and darkness conceals us	Reveals
414	301 (9)	From the thrones, she pursues what she has seen, # when she asks, and <u>is given</u> what <u>she desires</u>	Given
415			She asks
416	301 (11)	We struck them (Marj ibn Jahsh) # So <u>they did</u> not <u>stand</u> against him, nor <u>did they fight</u>	stand
417			They fought
418	301	<u>I say</u> to (Muta'im) when we met # And he had passed away, and in my hand was the sword:	I say
419	301 (14)	I bring you to the house of oppression, by force, # Humam <u>is</u> not oppressed, nor <u>is he subjugated</u> !	Oppressed
420			Sought
421	304 (2)	How <u>can you hope</u> for me to be silent, # when I have the permanent seat?	You hope
422	304 (5)	The night is a veil for lovers, # Oh, if only its moments <u>would last</u>	Last
423	304 (8)	With (Ramlatay Alaj) Rusum, # The artist's work <u>is prolonged</u> without it!	It lasts
424	306 (41)	And how <u>can one hope</u> for the generous to wake up, # if one day he becomes like him?	Hope
425	306 (15)	And whoever has lived peacefully and submitted to the will of the days, it is no wonder that his heart <u>has softened</u> !	Soften
426	310 (3)	And how <u>can one sleep</u> at night when his concern is # the pursuit of excellence in the pursuit of knowledge	Sleeps
427	310 (7)	He sleeps, and neither the virtuous can save him with his virtue, nor the imperfect with his imperfections.	Save

Imperfect verbs and their uses in the poetry of Abu Firas al Hamdani (a morphological and syntactic analysis)

428	310 (11)	When the days throw me into calamity # They pass and reveal the roar of the storm	Throw
429	310 (12)	And one day, <u>you will hear</u> thunder in its corners, # due to the intensity of the sounds of the qana and the humming	You think
430	310	So whoever wishes to be proud <u>will find</u> pride worthy of pride; # and whoever wishes to speak <u>will find</u> words worthy of a scholar!	He will find
431			He will find
432	311 (4)	And I cut off every thorn that no foot had touched # And no foot had trodden on its innermost part	Received
433	311 (5)	And I humiliated myself to the spears, and indeed, # he who did not <u>humiliate himself</u> among the spears was not honored.	Humiliate
434	311 (6)	And I saw my life, my delay in it <u>does not increase</u> , nor does my advancement enrich it.	Increases
435			Enrich
436	311 (13)	Some of our hearts were in his body # <u>so he would be</u> more stable than the hills (Yalamlam)	It would be
437	311 (16)	They wore iron despite themselves; and willingly # if only that <u>had not been</u> the case for them	be
438	311 (19)	Ask the people of (Kharashna) and their women will answer you # How many of them are widows, and how many are childless?	Answer
439	311 (23)	She is pregnant, and her husband is present at the wedding, # <u>pleasing</u> God, and her family is in mourning.	Pleasing
440	311 (25)	The glory of mankind, and you know that # only those who are determined <u>will attain</u> glory	Attain
441	311 (35)	And the return is Ahmad, and the nights are between us, # Tomorrow we will go, following them	We will go
442	311 (41)	If you remain in the iron, then as long as # you remain in the iron, <u>you will be placed</u> in the iron until the end	You will be placed
443	312 (1)	And a writer you chose to be Arabic # <u>Attributed</u> to the generous grandfather, and <u>Tamami</u>	Attributed
444	312 (3)	If I <u>had nothing</u> in you but that # with you I have been saved from committing the forbidden	Be
445	313 (1)	Listen, in the houses of (Bani Kilab), # (Bani al-Banna) <u>wailing over</u> (Tamim)	They mourn
446	314 (2)	His worries <u>linger</u> , and the night is dark, # He tosses	I stay

		and turns on the pricks of arrows	
447	314 (3)	The morning <u>turns</u> into morning, # And darkness turns into darkness	It leads
448	314 (5)	Wounds <u>that continue to come back</u> to me # for a wound that is still fresh, lasting	They continue
449			They come
450	314 (6)	And the throwing did not <u>remain</u> , even if it lingered # His nights passed like arrows	Remains
451	314 (7)	And by God, the defense, and which arrow # <u>I try</u> to repel, and God is the archer?	I try
452	314 (9)	Do you deny me as if you do not <u>know</u> # that I am that hero, the defender	You know
453	314 (12)	And you <u>saw</u> the patience, <u>and</u> claimed it # So the spear hastened you from speaking	You see
454			You claim
455	314 (14)	And <u>I will not be satisfied with</u> the boy unless he completes, # in the opinion of the old man, the courage of the young man	I am satisfied
456	314 (17)	And she covers him with a cloak, # <u>competing</u> with the huge spiders	Compete
457	314 (18)	They have the appearance of donkeys, so <u>you will not find</u> # a young man among them <u>walking</u> without a belt	You will not find
458			Walking
459	314 (19)	They <u>point out</u> flaws, and they are powerless # What <u>flaw is there</u> in the sword?	They praise
460			There is
461	314 (21)	<u>I address</u> every drum, # broad-chinned, slobbering	I address
462	314 (22)	<u>I refuse</u> , absolved of all faults, # and I become safe from all blame	I refuse
463	318 (3)	She departed, and her companion is present at the wedding, # <u>pleasing</u> to God, and her family is in mourning	Pleasing
464	320	O sons of Ka'b! By what misfortune # <u>do you</u> seek, O red-nosed ones! My position?	You seek
465	324 (2)	And if you pass by a gathering that the people of foolishness <u>do</u> not frequent, then sit with us!	Frequent
466	324 (3)	<u>We will</u> slaughter her in the fierce attack # Until she	We

		thirsts, in the neighborhoods, our shepherds	change
467	324 (5)	<u>And we redeem</u> the heap, scattered and terrified # Trusting only our enemies for safety	We redeem
468	324 (6)	And the guest becomes our master in our home # <u>We</u> <u>accept</u> that, and his judgment <u>prevails</u> over us	We are satisfied
469			He proceeds
470	329 (1)	<u>It is wrong</u> of me to name myself # And he has taken the qana from them and from us	It is wrong
471	329 (2)	So say to the doctor: If <u>I had</u> not <u>named</u> myself, the sword would have named me for them, and they would have called me	Name
472	331 (1)	Ask the girls of this neighborhood about me # <u>They</u> <u>will say</u> what they have seen and heard	They will say
473	331 (5)	I accepted the excuses and what they said. And if I became disobedient to them,	They say
474	331 (7)	And returning to me, <u>she says</u> secretly: # <u>I return</u> to his advice, damn him	She says
475			I return
476	331 (8)	When <u>she found</u> no hope, she turned away, # and said about me, reproachfully, "Say	Find
477	331 (9)	Have you seen what my cousins <u>say</u> # when women describe their husbands!	You say
478	331 (10)	By God, they do not touch them, alas, # they fabricate words and apologize for them	They touch
479	331 (11)	But I will describe <u>them</u> # and simplify their words of praise	I will find
480	335	I was stingy with myself, lest <u>it be said</u> that I was stingy # And I was cowardly, lest <u>it be said</u> that I was a coward	It is said
481			It is said
482	343 (18)	And a wave of foam <u>that confuses</u> the cat # I passed it with dignity, submissive	Confused
483	343 (19)	<u>It folds</u> the field with four braids # And spreads the wind with the damlan	Folds
484	343 (23)	And when I set out for a need, I am not deterred # by fear of retribution, nor by the passage of time	Deter
485	344 (2)	<u>And he sees</u> the help of the generous as chivalry, # which the vicissitudes of time have not diminished.	He sees
486	344 (3)	And <u>he melts</u> with secrecy, except that # his circumstances <u>reveal</u> his secrecy	He melts
487			Reveal

Imperfect verbs and their uses in the poetry of Abu Firas al Hamdani (a morphological and syntactic analysis)

488	344	When it is revealed, and his condition fades away, I find him <u>complaining</u> with every tongue	complaining
489	352 (3)	If <u>you are</u> innocent of his crime, # then whoever supported the offender is the offender.	Be
490	352 (8)	So I kept <u>praising</u> the horses, # with every ounce of hatred in my heart,	I bent
491	353 (20)	<u>He throws us</u> , half the country, mourners, # The truth of hatred, the excess of kindness	He throws
492	353 (21)	A country, by your life, <u>I have not left</u> its visitors # With a master who is harsh, harsh, harsh	Remove
493	353 (22)	We <u>will find</u> the speech in you and others # With success, at the time of the speeches, suffering	We encounter
494	353 (27)	It was fate, and <u>I had</u> no recourse # Fate overcame the courage of the brave	Be
495	353 (32)	If <u>I were</u> not so old, I would have # the opinion of the elders and the strength of the young.	Be
496	353	Time <u>passes</u> , and I have not found a companion # except for a treacherous one	Time passes
497	353 (36)	But (the sword of the state) the master whom <u>I have</u> not forgotten, and I see that he does not forget me	Forget
498			I see
499			Forget
500	353 (37)	Will those who <u>have</u> always <u>been</u> my protectors forget me, # out of generosity, and will those who have exalted me humiliate me?	He will lose
501			Yazal
502	353 (38)	The faithful one, and no one else, # <u>is satisfied</u> to help me in my distress.	He is satisfied
503	353 (39)	I <u>am jealous</u> of my place when I <u>see</u> # men who do not fill my place	I am jealous
504			I see
505	353 (40)	Or that <u>there be</u> a battle or a raid # My money has no effect with the young men	Be
506	353 (41)	And I knew, even if I called you, that if I slept without you, <u>I would sleep</u> without being awake.	I sleep
507	353 (42)	O rider, <u>throw</u> (the shield) with a bold, swift, and decisive throw!	Yarmi
508	353 (47)	(Sword of Guidance)! From the edge of your sword, <u>it is hoped</u> # A day will come that will humiliate disbelief for the sake of faith	is hoped for

509	353 (48)	These armies are <u>marching</u> toward your lands # Surrounded by disbelief and crosses	Marching
510	353 (64)	You are still here, O Sword of Guidance! <u>You meet</u> the enemy # with victorious fighting and wise counsel	You meet
511	364 (1)	It shines upon us when it rises, and it <u>sets</u> when the night falls.	It closes
512	364 (2)	Like the letter alif, he left him, lowering his eyelids until he saw him.	He sees
513	373 (3)	Who <u>stands up</u> for others, # between the rows, in my place?	Stand
514	373 (5)	<u>I protect</u> my family from <u>harm</u> , # but I do not <u>protect</u> my wealth!	I protect
515			Permitted
516			I protect
517	373 (6)	And you fear me, O people of the tribe of Liqa # H, and you have secured my enemies	Fear
518	373 (7)	You touch, when the night falls # F, her courtyard with my courtyard	Tumsī
519	373 (11)	He reaps, and no <u>one reaps</u> on his behalf, and <u>he fears</u> the great ones with him!	He reaps
520			He reaps
521			He fears

CONCLUSION

This research aims to study the use of defective present tense verbs in poems related to pride in the Diwan of Abu Firas al-Hamdani. Based on the results of the research, the researcher concluded that there are a total of 521 defective present tense verbs in poems related to pride in the Diwan of Abu Firas al-Hamdani.

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